

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DANIEL-EBUNE****FIRST NAME: ONYILOKO ENE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows 10

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Period 1 of the course, ACA-401D focused on the essential concepts of academic writing. The course pack was divided into several chapters with each chapter presenting closely related concepts. The course pack discussed a wide range of concepts including essay writing, plagiarism, rules of thumb for writing papers, literature review, style guides, the use of American vs. British English, and so forth.

Academic writing is different than other writings as it ‘aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence’(EUCLID 2019, 1). Academic writing is also expected to present examples that are apt with evidence that provide support for the idea under discussion as well as credible information in a way that the sources from which these are obtained are acknowledged to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5). My response paper will discuss a few of the concepts that I learnt for the first time and some of which have impacted my writing already.

2) CONCEPTS

a) Essay writing

One of the concepts that resonated with me was essay writing. I learnt the need to draw up a plan to serve as a guide for organizing my thoughts and response to any question; although, I am mindful that having a plan does not guarantee success in essay writing always and in any other area for that matter. However, a plan serves to streamline one’s thoughts and guide the research work to be carried out. Another feature of academic writing is that it is based on research work which provides evidence and

knowledge that is developed into argument as response to the question (EUCLID 2019, 2). Furthermore, ‘essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking’ (ibid.). Personally, this implies that even as I engage in academic writing using all the rules and styles, I will also need to deploy critical thinking skills as well as creativity in the process which should end in unique scholarly pieces.

b) Plagiarism

Every academic writer must be wary of plagiarism. Plagiarism is when writers do not properly cite the author or source of the information they have used (EUCLID 2019, 6). Although the concept of plagiarism is not new to me but what I found new and confusing was the second form of plagiarism which is said to occur when one ‘takes ideas from a source without footnoting the source’ (EUCLID 2019, 16). So my question here is that, do you only footnote the source without an in-text citation? Moreover, the prescribed solution to plagiarism is that the source of information should be appropriately cited. I am still trying to reconcile these two. In the same vein, I am still grappling with the circumstances in which one does not need to cite the source of information. Somehow, I feel that I have not fully grasped the concept of plagiarism.

c) The use of American vs. British English

Some of the reasons that were adduced for the prevalent use of American English include the size of the publishing industry in America, the wealth of the U.S. economy and its influences, the global outreach of mass media as well as its influence, et cetera. I was surprised to see that the use of periods, commas and quotation marks were different and marked “extremely important” (EUCLID 2019, 35). This gets trickier for me at this stage because of the several categories of differences between standard American English and standard British English (EUCLID 2019, 27). I believe that the use of either of these standards is a matter of requirement or personal choice as the case may be. I also think that this reiterates the need for the use of style guides as well as deployment of creative and critical thinking skills.

d) Some Rules of Thumb for writing papers

This Chapter in the course pack made a profound impact on me. The suggestions shared here were very apt and helped me to understand how to write academic papers better. Personally, chief among the tips was that the use of first person singular was acceptable (EUCLID 2019, 16). This is a very great departure from the regular norm which I have been taught before now. I even took some time while studying to recall instances where I struggled to find proper expressions of what I felt about a topic but had to leave that part out because I could not find the appropriate expression. I believe that the use of the first person singular helps writers to capture their experiences in their writings and express themselves better.

e) Using Chicago Style

The formatting of books and research papers using the style found in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) 2003 has been referred to as Chicago style (EUCLID 2019, 44). The CMS crib sheet is said to contain the Chicago style and how to use it with respect to abbreviations and acronyms, capitalization, compound words, emphasis using italics and/or quotes, numbers and dates, as well as quotations. The sheet also contains Chicago page formatting and end/footnotes as well as the Chicago Bibliographies. The use of Chicago style seemed familiar to me as I had used many of its rules before now, for example, the introduction of acronyms by placing them in parenthesis immediately after the source phrase (*ibid.*). However, one aspect of the Chicago style I found fascinating was the use of scholarly abbreviations. I learnt for the first time that scholarly abbreviations such as *etc.*, *e.g.*, and *i.e.* are to be used only in parenthetical comments and are to be spelt out when they are not in parentheses (*ibid.*).

3) CONCLUSION

Putting together all I have learnt in this period, I fully appreciate the huge difference in academic or scholarly writing compared to other types of writing. I also realized that, in as much as academic writing has rules and styles to guide the writer, there is still room for personal style and creativity.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.